

Morpheme Repetition where two Syllables Repeat the Meaning

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ABSTRACT: Composite words with repetition meaning have the form of a repeating morpheme and are generally classified in categories as reduplicative words. However, the composite words with repetition meaning and reduplicative words are fundamentally different. The reduplicative word is created by converting phonetic from the original syllable and the generated word has a different meaning from the original. Meanwhile, the composite words that have repeating meanings are two different words randomly compounded. Among reduplicative words can be derived from phonetic variations between dialects.

Composite words with repetition meaning have the form of repeating part or all of a syllable that is also reduplicative of the initial consonant and the rhyme of the word but is not derived from the repetition mechanism. This type of composite words meaning completely repeats and repeats some meaning means. The reduplicative words use the morphemes and words composite method but the word's repetition meaning has the form of both repetition meaning and reduplicative words. Reduplicative words and repetition words are common in many languages around the world but composite words with repetition meaning have the form of repeating phonetic are still not popular.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Vietnamese is often considered to be monosyllabic as its morphemes are considered to be monosyllabic. In Vietnamese, syllable, morpheme and single words overlap. For example, the word “nước” (water) is one syllable and a single word, but in the composite word “đất nước” (country), it is a morpheme. Most Vietnamese morphemes consist of only one syllable and it's also a single word. A Vietnamese word may consist of a single morpheme or more than one morpheme. Polymorphemic words are either composite words or words consisting of stems plus affixes or reduplicants.

However, some Vietnamese words may consist of one or more syllables, composed of monosyllabic morphemes that form together to create another word. Composite words with repetition meaning are a kind of equal composite word. In terms of meaning, this composite word has complete repetition and repeats some meanings. For a long time, a number of Vietnamese researchers have confused reduplicative words and compound words with repetition meaning have the form of repeating the syllable by not studying their meaning thoroughly. Reduplicative words have two morphemes, usually, the second morpheme repeats the phonetic of the first morpheme (original word) and the meaning of the second morpheme is the nuance or emotive meaning.

Partial or full syllable reduplication is common in languages of the world, especially Austroasiatic languages. Abbi thinks “Reduplication may also refer to the iteration of syllables that constitute a single word lexeme. It acquires this status only after it is reduplicated. In such cases, the repetition of syllables itself constitutes a word or a lexical item. I would like to term them 'expressives' (following Diffioth [1976]) and define them by saying that expressions are instances of morphological reduplication where the minimally meaningful and segmentally indivisible morphemes are constituted of iterated syllables. Thus, the base and the iterated part together constitute a single-morpheme”. (Abbi, A. 1990.)

However, compound words with repetition meaning are completely different. Composite words with repetition meaning have the form of repeating syllables just due to the sound change or random repeating sound, not the method of reduplicative words. Composite words with repetition meaning are also different from compound words with repetition phonetic. Composite words with repetition sounds are random compound words and the second morpheme does not create the nuance of meaning like reduplicative words and compound words with repetition meaning. Compound words with repetition meaning have two kinds: the

kind of the repeating meaning has form reduplicative and the kind of repeating meaning without form reduplicative. Diep Quang Ban, Hoang Van Thung. 2012, p.50-51 and Nguyen Tai Can.1996, p.93-99 call a compound word with reduplicative meaning. This can also be called syllables repetition where two morphemes repeat the meaning has the form of a reduplicative word.

In Vietnamese, there is a kind of compound word repetition of meaning. This type of compound word has two forms: two repeating morphemes and two repeating different morphemes. The type of repeating morphemes has the appearance of the reduplicative word but means repeat. The two morphemes of the word repeat the initial consonant: Bó buộc (bind tie), the meaning of the two forms of this word is near the meaning, "tie" is the method of the "bind".

The implicit meaning of this word is to be attached and lose freedom. Bò bịch (barrel bag), are two instruments to contain something, these two forms both have metaphorical meanings are lover. Meanwhile, bồng bế (carry), both mean "hold in one's arms". Two morphemes of word rhyme gemination: binh lính, bợ đỡ, bút rút. Two morphemes of the word "binh lính" both mean "soldier". The word "bợ đỡ" (faw raise), these two forms both have a metaphorical meaning is "flattery". Word "bút rút", these two morphemes have meaning "tear", their implicit meaning is uneasy. Meanwhile, the morphemes of the reduplicative words do not repeat the meaning mentioned above.

According to Nguyễn Tài Căn, there are words that used to belong to composite words with repetition meaning but now change to compound words with repetition phonetic, such as "hỏi han" (ask question), "tuổi tác" (age age). These are compound words with repetition meaning have the form of repeating initial consonants (Nguyễn Tài Căn. 1996, p.89 -99). For such cases as "tóc tai" (hair ear), "mương máng" (ditch gutter), "môi má" (lip cheek), "núi non" (mountain hill), "trắng trong" (white clear), "phố phường" (urban quarter) ... are reduplication department words (Đỗ Thị Kim Liên.1999, p.34-35) but we think these are isosceles compound words with repetition of meaning a form of reduplication department.

Composite words have the form of the reduplicative words: repeating the two Sino-Vietnamese elements, repeating an old Sino-Vietnamese and Sino-Vietnamese element, repeating a Sino-Vietnamese element and variant Sino-Vietnamese, repeating a Vietnamese element and old Vietnamese. A variant of Sino-Vietnamese is called Sino-Vietnameseization by some linguists as Vũ Đức Nghiệu (2011, 163-171). It is actually a phenomenon of phonetic variation, the phonetic transformation from one Sino-Vietnamese sound to another according to the rules of phonetic transformation but it still retains Sino-Vietnamese sounds without losing its accent like ancient Sino-Vietnamese words. Wang's (1948:63, 76-77 and 1958:380-381), the groundbreaking articles on Sino-Vietnamese historical linguistics, he offered no phonological explanation but categorized these as nativized forms following Vietnamese pronunciation, what he termed 越化 *yuè huà* 'Vietnamized', which suggests that these were loanwords modified later after borrowing from Chinese. Previously, this layer was called 古漢越字 'Old Sino-Vietnamese' by Wang Li (1948), recently, however, Phan (2013), in an extensive study of Sino-Vietnamese, chose the term 'Early Sino-Vietnamese' to avoid confusion with the use of 'old' for reconstructions of proto-languages. Compound words have the form of reduplicative words are random reduplicative

Composite words with repetition meaning have the form of repeating phonetic has two forms of repetition meaning: complete repetition and repetition of some meanings. However, Vietnamese researchers have not studied this compound word thoroughly, but only initially classified and described it briefly. So, we write this article to clearly distinguish the types of compound words mentioned above. The article clearly analyzes morphological features and the meaning structure of the word compound meaning that has the form of repeating the syllable.

2. CONTENT

2.1. Distinguish reduplicative words and composite words by repeating the meaning

In linguistics, repeat is a process of creating a form of words. However, the morphology of repeating word has two forms and there are differences between them. The first form is a reduplicative word in which the root of a word or part of it, even the whole word is repeated or with a slight change. In the second form, composite words have the form of the reduplicative word, but completely repetition of the meaning of a word or some of the meanings of the word. This form is a composite word in which two morphemes have repeated meanings.

The first form is common in languages around the world. It is often used when a speaker adopts a tone expressive and figurative iconic in meaning than ordinary speech. Reduplication is reduplicated segment sequences of consonants or vowels. The reduplication words are usually created in two ways: One is in the form of duplicated segments sequence of consonants or vowels and the second is in the form of duplicated morpheme. Reduplicative words have in a wide range of languages and language groups with different levels level.

2.1.1. Reduplicative word

a. Rhyming reduplication:

In Vietnamese: bơ vơ (desolate, lonely), cấp rập (hasty), chon von (sky high), hấp tấp (hurried), lương vương (entanglement)... There is also the form of words that combine 3 morphemes, or even 4 morphemes. Kind of three morphemes: xốp (styrofoam) > xốp xốp (very styrofoam) > xốp xồm xốp (very styrofoam), mờ (blurry) > tờ mờ (slightly blurred) > lơ tờ mờ

(can't see anything). Kind of four morphemes: vội (hurry) > vội vàng (hurry) > vội vội vàng vàng (very hurry), bồn bồn (fret) > bồn bồn bồn bồn (very fret) (Hoàng Văn Hành. 1985, P. 62-67).

In South Asian Languages: In Indonesian: sayur-mayur: 'vegetables' (sayur means 'vegetables'), lauk-pauk: 'side dishes' (lauk means 'side dishes'), kaya-raya: 'rich' (kaya means 'rich'), ramah-tamah: 'hospitable and friendly' (ramah means 'hospitable and friendly') (Goddard, Cliff. 2005).

In English, there is a similar form: Boogie-woogie, easy-peasy, hanky-panky, hocus-pocus, hoity-toity, hokey-pokey, hurdy-gurdy, itsy-bitsy, namby-pamby, raggie-taggle, ragtag, razzle-dazzle, super-duper, teenie-weenie, willy-nilly, wingding. (Donka Minkova. 2002).

b. Initial consonant reduplication:

Initial consonant reduplication but change vowel and final consonant in Vietnamese words: buồn bã (very sad) hốt hải (panic), lạnh lùng (coldly), nhí nhảnh (playful), no nê (very satiety), vu vơ (aimless), ... In English words: chit-chat, hip-hop, ding-dong, jibber-jabber, kitty-cat, knick-knack, ping-pong, pitter-patter, sing-song, splish-splash, zig-zag, flip-flop, flimflam, wibble-wobble. (Donka Minkov, May 2002).

Initial reduplication in Agta: [ɸurab] 'afternoon' → [ɸuɸurab] 'late afternoon' (ɸu-ɸurab), [ŋaŋaj] 'a long time' → [ŋaŋaŋaj] 'a long time (in years)' (ŋa-ŋaŋaj), (Healey 1960)

In South Asian Languages: Indonesian: laki (husband) > lelaki (man), lara (sick) > lelara (illness); Khmer: louk (sale) > lolouk (cry for sale) (Nguyễn Thiện Giáp. 2011, p.27).

c. Completely repeat two morphemes:

Method reduplication is used in inflections to convey a grammatical function, and in lexical derivation to create new words. In reduplication, the reduplicant is most often repeated only once, but in some languages, reduplication can occur more than once, resulting in a tripled form. The a slight decrease in comparison with the original meaning of the word: In Vietnamese: xanh (green) > "xanh xanh" (green green): hơi xanh (bluish), điên (crazy) > điên điên (hơi điên) (crazy crazy, daft). Loop has tonal variation: đỏ (red) > đỏ đỏ (reddish), trắng (white) > trắng trắng (whitish), vàng (yellow) > vàng vàng (yellowish), vui (be joyful) > vui vui (jovial, fun), nghiêng (inclined) > nghiêng nghiêng (slightly slanted). The phenomenon of borrowing English pronunciation follows follow Vietnamese "mad" (crazy) > mát mát (chập chập) (crazy crazy) > mát mát chập chập (a little crazy, not normal nerves).

The reduplication word is common in Southeast Asian languages: Exact reduplications in Indonesian: api (fire) > apiapi (matchstick), fotsy (white) > fotsyfotsy (slightly white); Lao language: tằm tằm (slightly low), hom hom (very fragrant). In Indonesian: touc-touc ('small' used for several of the same item), chruu-chruu: ('deep' used for several instances); Thai: dèk-dèk ('child-child' ['children']); Indonesia/Malay: anak-anak ('child-child' ['children']), lalat-lalat ('fly-fly' ['flies']); (Goddard, Cliff. 2005).

In English words: Ack ack, aye-aye, back-to-back, blah-blah, boo-boo, bye-bye, chin-chin, choo-choo, chow-chow, dik-dik, doo-doo, fifty-fifty, gogo, ha ha, half-and-half, housey-housey, juju, klop-klop, mama, muumuu, night-night, no-no, papa, pee-pee, pip-pip, pom-pom, poo-poo, pooh-pooh, putt putt, so-so, ta-ta, tut-tut, tutu, wah-wah, wee-wee, yo-yo. (Donka Minkova. 2002).

Repeat words to denote superlatives: in Russian, reduplication methods based on factors stem can be used to render meaningful comparison of absolute levels of adjectives: добрый (kind), добрый-добрый (the best kind); большой (big), большой-большой (big biggest). (Nguyễn Đức Tồn. 2011, p. 4).

Repeat words to denote the grammatical meanings of the plural: In Vietnamese for this repetition: Ngành ngành "career career", người người "people people". However, the structures such as "ngày ngày" (day day), "sáng sáng" (morning morning), "đêm đêm" (night night), "chiều chiều" (afternoon afternoon) are not compound word structures but are grammatical structures denoting repeating time. They indicate the progression of time: day to day, morning to morning, afternoon to afternoon, night to night. This form of repetition indicates grammatical meaning not a reduplicative word. This type is used in formal Vietnamese, especially in literature: "Ngày ngày em đứng em trông, Trông non non ngất, trông sông sông dài" (ca dao) 'Day to day you stood you looked, Looking mountains high mountains, looking river long river' (folk poetry).

This orthography has resurfaced widely in text messaging and other forms of electronic communication. Chinese also uses reduplication: 人 rén for "person", 人人 rénrén for "everybody". Japanese does it too: 時 toki "time", tokidoki 時々 "sometimes, from time to time". Both languages can use a specially written iteration mark 々 to indicate reduplication, although in Chinese the iteration mark is no longer used in standard writing and is often found only in calligraphy. Japanese does it too: 時 toki "time", tokidoki 時々 "sometimes, from time to time". In the Turkish language, emphatic reduplication: A word can be reduplicated partially, such that an emphatic stem is created to be attached to the adjective. This is done by taking the first syllable of the adjective, dropping the syllable-final phoneme, and adding one of four interpolated consonants (p, s, m, r). For example, kırmızı (red) becomes kıpkırmızı (very red); mavi (blue) becomes masmavi (very blue). A word can be reduplicated totally, giving a related but different meaning or used for emphasizing. For example, zaman zaman (time time) meaning "occasionally"; uzun uzun (long long) meaning "very long or many things long" (Göksel, Asli & Kerlake, Celia (2005).

Japanese also contains a large number of mimetic words formed by reduplication of a syllable: These words include not only onomatopoeia, but also words intended to invoke non-auditory senses or psychological states, such as きらきら kirakira (sparkling or shining). By one count, approximately 43% of Japanese mimetic words are formed by full reduplication. (Tamamura, Fumio.1979, p. 208–216. And 1989, p. 23–51). Many others are formed by partial reduplication, as in がささ~ ga-sa-sa- (rustling) (Nasu, Akio. 2003, p. 210–221). Indonesia/Malay: anak-anak ('child-child' ['children']), lalat-lalat ('fly-fly' ['flies']). Thai: dèk-dèk ('child-child' ['children']). Myanmar [Tibeto-Burman]: səl səl ('boys boys' [səl means 'boys']). Case plural to plural. Japanese (Sino-Tibetan):人々 hitobito ('people'). The word is written by using iteration '々' which indicates duplication. The form is also using rendaku, where 'h' in hito should be paired with 'b' in the reduplication syllable bito. In the Malayo-Polynesian family language, reduplication is used to form plurals: rumah "house", rumah-rumah "houses". In pre-1972, Indonesian and Malaysian orthography, two was shorthand for the reduplication that forms plurals: orang "person", orang-orang or orang 2 "people". (Omar, Asmah Haji. 1989, p. 9–13).

2.1.2. The method of word formation

The structure reduplicative: Random compound words such as “ba ba” (tortoise), “buom bướm” (butterfly), “cào cào” (locust), “châu châu” (grasshopper), “chôm chôm” (rambutan), “chuồn chuồn” (dragonfly), “đu đu” (papaya), “đười ươi” (orangutan), “nòng nọc” (tadpole), “thòn bơn” (flounder). This type is derived from ancient Vietnamese, one of the two double consonants is turned into a syllable of a word or a double syllable of the word. This is a word form where two morphemes combine randomly.

The phenomenon of pseudo-reduplication, changes of double consonants opening syllables in ancient Vietnamese: Example: pair l-nh / (m/tr): *mlâm due to the loss -m variation in the opening double consonant, there should be “lâm” and by entering two consonants ml → nh, so there is “nhâm” (unfounded), then these two variant syllables are paired together in a somatic relationship so there is “lâm nhâm” (talk nonsense). Pair l / r - c (k): * klò → “lò” and “cò” should have “lò cò” (hopscotch)... (Nguyễn Đức Tồn. 2016, p.1-19). Forms of transfer sound from Khmer into Vietnamese: “tlum” (full) > “tùm lum, um tùm” (many, dense); “chhêh” > “chêh êhêh” (straddle); “chho” > “chò hó” > “chôm hỏm” (squat) (Đỗ Hữu Châu.1997, p.153-160).

Two elements with the same sound simulation: ào ào, oang oang (clarion), ðoàng ðoàng, choang choang (banging), rầm rầm (roaring). These are the words that simulate the sound, not reduplicative words but acoustic coupler words or alliteration.

2.1.3. Compound words have the form of repeating morpheme in Vietnamese

The reduplication words and compound words with repetition of meaning have different in that, reduplication word is a main - minor composite word but compound words with repetition of meaning is an isosceles compound word. The reduplication words in which one morpheme has the main meaning and the second one has the secondary meaning, nuanced meaning. Meanwhile, in the word compounding meaning, the two morphemes are both isomorphic meaning. With reduplication words, the morpheme is not independent in speaking activities, but the word compounding means the two morphemes are inherently single words operating freely in communication. Words with repeating sounds have the form of reduplication words but they have no nuance of meaning. If the reduplicative words have complete reduplication and part reduplication then the compound words also repeats some meaning and repeats meaning completely. It is the similarity in meaning between reduplicated words and compound words that makes researchers confuse these two types.

2.2. The mechanism in compound words with repeating of meaning has the form of the reduplicative word

2.2.1. Initial consonant reduplication

Noun: Bâu bạn 伴 (friend friend), câu cú 句 (sentence sentence), chim chóc (birds gizzard), chùa chiền (temple pagoda), hàng hóa 貨 (goods commodity), hầm hào 壕 (tunnel trench), hình 形 hài 骸 (shape portrait), lời lãi (profit interest) lỗi lầm (error mistake), mồ mã (grave tomb), nghề nghiệp 業 (career profession), rừng rú (forest jungle), thánh 聖 thần 神 (divinity omnipotent), thê 妻 thiếp 妾 (wife concubine), tiền 錢 tệ 幣 (money currency)...

Verb: Bao 包 bọc (envelop wrap), châm 針 chích (prick sting), chát chồng (heap overlap), di 移 dời (move displaced), dụ 誘 dỗ (entice coax), đánh đập (beat hit), đo đạc 度 (measure mete), ho hen (cough asthma cough), hội 會 họp (meet gather), lẫn lộn (confuse mistake), leo trèo (climb creep), lượm lặt (pick gather), mộng 夢 mơ (dream dream), nghi 疑 ngờ (doubt suspect), sinh 生 sống (be born, live), soi sáng (shine flash), thay thế 替 (replace change), thích thú 趣 (enjoy rejoice), tiếp 接 tục (continue go on), trốn tránh (hide avoid)...

Adjective: Cuối cùng 窮 (final last), cương 僵 cứng (turgid hard), dẻo dai (flexible tough), đông đặc (frozen condensed), đơn 單 độc 獨 (single alone), hèn hạ 下 (cowardly low), hư hỏng (corrupt broken), khổ 困 khổ 苦 (miserable destitute), nhu 柔 nhược 弱 (sybaritic frail), sung 充 sướng 暢 (many happy), thông 常 thường 常 (common, normal), tồi 毀 (hủy) tàn 殘 (bad shabby), xiêu ẹo (oblique inclined)...

2.2.2. Rhyming reduplication

Noun: Binh 兵 lính (army soldier), giá 價 cả (price cost), sức 力 lực (strength force), thứ 次 tự 序 (ordinal order), tội 罪 lỗi (sin error)....

Verb: Can 諫 諫 (dissuade expostulate), cạnh 諫 tranh 爭 (compete emulate), chán ản (bored discouraged), chia lia (divide separate), mong ngóng (looking forward to expecting), quát nạt (shout bullying), sa ngã (drop fall), so đọ (compare collate), soi rọi (flash beam), tranh 爭 giành (compete for dispute), trú 住 ngụ 寓 (inhabit reside)...

Adjective: Cao 高 ngạo 傲 (high arrogant), căng thẳng (taut straight), cần 勤 mẫn 勵 (diligent laborious), chênh vênh (tilted warped), lân 邻 cận 近 (neighbouring next), méo xẹo (distorted slanting), thân 親 cận 近 (intimate near), vắng lặng (quiet silent)....

2.3. Types of compound words with repeated meanings

2.3.1. Completely repetition meaning

Noun: Bâu bạn: "bâu": Muong language means "bâu", meaning "bạn" (friend), but when compounding with "bạn", according to the law of counterpoint, the tone is converted from gliding tone to plain tone. Câu cú: "câu" (sentence) is "cú" (sentence) 句, sentence "câu nói" 語句 (communication sentence). Thus, "câu" and "cú" are derived from the Sino-Vietnamese language but read differently, written in the same way. Chim chóc: (bird gizzard): "choc": old Vietnamese also means "bird", Nom letters write 祝 "chóc". Giá cả: (price cost): value, price, Sino-Vietnamese 价 is also written as 價; "cả" is the old sound of "giá" (price). Lãi lãi: (profit interest) "lãi" (interest) is also "lãi" (profit), the "lãi" is the local language of "lãi", referring to the amount of difference due to overspending in the trading process. Mộ mã (grave tomb): "mộ" (tomb) is "mả" (grave), possibly "mộ" (tomb), in Sino-Vietnamese, written 墓 because of going with "mả" "tomb", so between them have tones change, so "mộ" (tomb) also writes 墓. Nghề nghiệp: (career profession), "nghệp" (career) is also "nghề" (profession), Sino-Vietnamese writing 業, farming: 業 農. Tuổi tác: (age, year of age), "tác" (age) in ancient Vietnamese is also "tuổi" (age), a term for age each person of life.

Verb: Bao bọc: (envelop wrap), forming a shield, "bao" (envelop): Sino-Vietnamese written 包 envelop, wrapping: 一包 香煙 A pack of cigarettes; 兩包 大米 Two bags of rice. "Wrap": package, sealed. Chơi nhời: "chơi" (play), "nhời" is also "chơi" (play), the dialect of "play". Đo đạc (measure mete), "đạc" (measure) is "đo" (mete), written in Sino-Vietnamese 度, Nom sound is "đo" 擲. Hỏi han (ask, ask for): "han": Muong means "hỏi" (ask), "ask" just asking to know. Leo trèo (climb): moving the body up, "leo" (climbing) is the local sound of "trèo" (climb). Mộng mơ: "mộng" (dream): Sino-Vietnamese written 夢. "Mộng" (Dreaming) is a dream, seeing things that while sleeping may or may not be in reality. Thay thế (replace change), "thay" (replace): Sino-Vietnamese writes 替, which also means "thế" (change) 代替 thay thế; "thay", Nom writes 替, removed, used for changing in another place or another person. Thích thú (enjoy rejoice) feeling excited satisfied, satisfied, Sino-Vietnamese write "thú" 趣, hứng thú 興趣, "thích", Nom letters write 感.

Adjective: Lanh lợi: "lợi" (quick): agile, in Sino-Vietnamese written 俐. "Lanh" is the universal sound of "fast". Maybe the word "lanh" (agile) turns sound into "linh": flexible 伶俐. "Quick" in the popular "agile", so "agile" has variations: linh lệ, lanh lợi, linh lợi, lanh lệ (agile, quick, flexible, fast). Lân cận (neighboring next): "cận" (near), Sino-Vietnamese written 近. "Lân" (next) is adjacent, Sino-Vietnamese written 邻, nearby, next to: 鄰國 neighboring country. Rảnh rỗi (free time): "rảnh" (free): in the state of having no work to do, not being busy; "rỗi" is the local sound of "rảnh".

2.3.2. Repeat some meaning

Noun: Hầm hào (tunnel trench), "hào" (trench): Sino-Vietnamese for 壕 is also "tunnel", Vietnamese sound, Nom write 窖. "A tunnel" in Vietnamese is a deep hole dug into the ground, with or without a cover used to hide. The "hào" (trench) is a wide, deep and long trench that can be walked around. Nồi niêu (Pot) "nồi" (pot): utensils used to cook food in general, "niêu" is a kind of small earthenware pot. But so, the "niêu" is a kind of "nồi" (pot). Thê 妻 thiếp 妾 (wife concubine), "thê" (wife): the first wife, Sino-Vietnamese write chồng và vợ (husband and wife) 夫 (phu) 妻 (thê); "thiếp" (concubine) is a concubine, both images refer to the wife in general.

Verb: Chán nản (bored depressed), "chán" (bored): in a state of no longer craving anything. "Nản" (depressed) : in the state of not wanting to do anything. "Chán" (bored) leads to "depressed" and also "discouraged" should lead to depression. Chát chồng (Heap pile): "Chát" (Heap) put on each other many layers into large blocks; "chồng" (pile overlap) put one next to the other by height. If you want to "chát" (heap), you must "chồng" (overlap), and you must stack things up vertically. Chia lia (divide separate) "divided": made into parts from a whole body; "liã": leaving one body, one group. "Chia" (dividing) will lead to separation, "liã" (separate) is the result of the division. Giảng giải (explain solve): Sino-Vietnamese writes 講, explain, tell people to understand clearly what is called lecture. "Giải" (solve): Sino-Vietnamese writes 解, explain: 解答 問題 answer the problem. Want to "teach", it is necessary to "solve" and "solve" is to "teach". Lỗi lầm: (error mistake), "lỗi": errors due to not complying with regulations or techniques, "mistakes": wrong perception, recognizing one for another. "Mistake" leads to "error" or can also

"mistake" by the "error". "Lỗi lầm" are mistakes, flaws. Trông mong (look, wait with eagerness): "Trông": towards whom, what with hope, expectation; "mong" in the state of waiting for, waiting for someone, or something. "Trông" (looking) has many meanings, but going with "mong" means expecting something. Trốn tránh (hide avoid): "Trốn" (hide) hiding in a secret place to avoid being seen, caught; "tránh" (avoid): move to another place so that no one can meet, or be free from disasters or violence. "To hide" is to avoid, the purpose of escape is to avoid something.

Adjective: Hèn hạ (cowardly low): "hạ" (low): Sino-Vietnamese write 下: low, 山下 under the mountain; 燈下 under the lights. "Hèn" (cowardly): in a low position. "Hèn" (cowardly) should be in the lower, lower than others. Hư hỏng (corrupt broken): "Hư" (corrupt) ruined, rotten; "hỏng" (broken) damaged, unusable, "hư" (corrupt) will lead to broken. Sung sướng (full happy), "sung" (many): written in Sino-Vietnamese 充, full, overflowing, "spirit of prosperity" 精神充足 spirit of fullness. "Sướng" (happy): there is a feeling of excitement and satisfaction. "Sướng" (happy) is due to "sung" (many), when full of well-being then people are "happy". Vắng lặng (quiet silent): "Lặng" (quiet): no people and animals lead to "silence": no sound and activity.

3. CONCLUSION

Reduplicative words and compound words with repetition of meaning are different in terms of structure and grammatical meanings. The reduplicative words are usually made up of a part of the root word, while a repeating word is a completely repeating syllable. The reduplicative words are created to show some meanings different from the meaning of the original word. Repeating words often make up the plural meaning. In Vietnamese, word repeating has the same formality as reduplicative words. It is a compound word with a repetition of meaning in the form of reduplicative phonetic. This type has the initial consonant reduplication and the rhyming reduplication. This is a form of coincidence by chance, not using the transcription method to create new words. There is a type that is the phonetic variation between the dialects to make the variation has a reduplication form. Example: "Lầm lẫn" (Mistake confuse): "lầm" (mistake) is the dialect of "lẫn" (confuse), in the North dialect "lầm" (mistake) is "nhầm" as a mistake: "nhầm lẫn". Lẫn lộn (Confuse): "lộn" (confuse), the local sound of "lẫn" (confuse). As such, they create complete synonyms for the words "lầm lẫn" (mistake), "nhầm lẫn" (mistake), and "lẫn lộn" (confuse).

Completely repetition meaning is usually synonyms pieced together from language variations such as "lầm lẫn", "nhầm lẫn", "lẫn lộn" (mistake confuse), and words of different linguistic origins as between Viet – Muong "bầu bạn" (friend friend), Vietnamese - Sino "nghề nghiệp" (career profession), modern Vietnamese and Ancient Vietnamese "tuổi tác" (age, year of age)... Repeat some strokes the meaning of the result, the meaning of the cause, and the meaning of the method. For example, the meaning of method in the word "chất chồng" (heap pile); the meaning of cause - results in the word "chia li" (divide separate), the meaning of the cause in the word "lỗi lầm" (error mistake). For the repeating nouns, there are common and specific meanings between the two elements such as "thê thiếp (wife concubine), "hầm hào" (tunnel trench) ...

Thus, compound words with repetition of meaning have the form of reduplicative sounds are a special phenomenon in the structure of Vietnamese words. This article mainly compares the reduplicative words and compound words with repetition of meaning have the form of reduplicative phonetic for the method of structure and mechanism of meaning. We will have the next article comparing compound words with repetition of meaning yes and no form of reduplicative sound; study of language exposure in compound words.

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